

Pupils', parents' and teachers' perceptions on unintended consequences of school closures during the COVID-19 pandemic in Austria - protocol of an exploratory survey

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1 Introduction

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, drastic measures were taken worldwide to contain the spread of the virus. These included school closures in many countries for varying lengths of time [1]. Pupils not attending school suddenly turned parents into tutors, disrupted the daily routines of families, and reduced in-person social contacts [2, 3]. As children and adolescents are at a vulnerable age regarding personal development, some studies reported negative consequences including increases in long-term mental health issues [4]. Examples are mental confusion, loneliness, depression and irritation to negative lifestyle habits, lifestyle disorders affecting eating, exercise behaviour, and sleep, experiences of violence or abuse, financial difficulties, decline in school performance and limited opportunities for social development [5, 6]. In the course of the research project "Being Equipped to Tackle Epidemics Right (BETTER)" unintended consequences of the pandemic school closures were identified for the Austrian context in the form of qualitative vignette study with diverse stakeholders and globally based on a scoping review among other effects of the COVID-19 containment measures [7, 8]. In Austria, surveys were conducted on the perceptions and experiences of pupils, parents and teachers regarding the changed learning modalities due to the COVID-19 pandemic school closures [9 - 11]. Local data on perceptions of unintended consequences is still lacking. Based on this gap of knowledge and the identification of unintended consequences through qualitative interview data and literature review, a follow-up study of the BETTER project shall investigate the perception of the found outcomes by pupils, parents and teachers.

Aim:

This exploratory survey aims to investigate the perception of pupils, their parents, and teachers on unintended consequences of COVID-19-related school closures in Austria.

Exploratory research questions:

1. Which statements from qualitative interview data have the strongest agreement among participants?
2. Which unintended consequences found in the scoping literature review have the greatest impact on pupils, according to the participants' perceptions?
3. Do participant groups differ in their prioritization of the most important unintended consequences?
4. How do levels of health literacy differ with regard to the perception of statement agreements and unintended consequences?

2 Methods

Study design

Cross-sectional exploratory survey on unintended consequences of school closures during the COVID-19 pandemic on pupils in Austria.

Participants

Eligible participants had to live in Austria, preferably in Vienna or Lower Austria, during the COVID-19 pandemic and give informed consent. The minimum age for participation is 14 years at the time of enrollment and participation in the online survey is voluntary.

Inclusion criteria:

- Participants residing in Austria, preferably in Vienna or Lower Austria, currently and during the COVID-19 pandemic
- Participants 14 years or older at the time of enrollment
- Participants providing informed consent
- Participants willing to complete the survey online

Specific criteria for participant subgroups

Pupils:

- Enrolled in school during the COVID-19 pandemic

Parents or Legal Guardians:

- Child welfare for at least one pupil enrolled in school during the COVID-19 pandemic

Teachers:

- Employment as a school teacher (currently and during the COVID-19 pandemic)

Exclusion criteria:

- Individuals unable to provide informed consent
- Individuals unable to complete the survey online
- Individuals younger than 14 years

Recruitment

Participants will be recruited using convenience sampling. The principals of schools, preferably in Vienna and Lower Austria will be contacted for possible participation in the anonymous survey study. The school partners (school forum or school community committee) of the current school must agree to the survey being conducted. For Vienna, this consent is based on the autonomous decision-making authority of the school partners of the respective school in accordance with § 46 para. 2 of the Austrian School Education Act (SchUG). If the school partners of the respective school decide to participate in this anonymous online survey, the information about this voluntary survey study will be forwarded by the school administration to the teachers, the parents' association and suitable pupils. The information consists of an introductory text of the anonymous online survey, information on informed consent and a web link to the anonymous online survey hosted on the SoSci online survey platform [12] via www.soscisurvey.de.

If individuals receiving the informational e-mail are interested in participating in this study, they can download and read the information letter (Informed Consent). If a person wishes to participate in the anonymous survey, the questionnaire can be accessed via the provided link. The link can be used to

download information and the informed consent once again before entering the data. If the individual clicks on "Ich möchte teilnehmen" (I would like to participate), they can enter their anonymous non health-related data. The advantage of anonymous data collection is that no person can be identified at any time. Participation in this anonymous survey study takes 15 minutes.

Data collection

A questionnaire developed for this exploratory cross-sectional anonymous survey study will be used to collect participants' non health-related data. The survey questionnaire includes questions about age in age groups, gender, the perspective from which the school closures were experienced, the federal state of the school and the place of residence and, in the latter case, the distinction between urban and rural areas.

In addition, agreement with statements on the impact of school closure measures during the COVID-19 pandemic from stakeholder vignette interviews at an earlier stage of the BETTER project is also queried [7]. The statements reflect important topics that were identified in the course of qualitative research study. Agreement with these statements by survey participants will be assessed using a five-point Likert scale. The statements and questions in German are on the topics of investment in education, social inequality, distance learning as an alternative and long-term consequences of social development.

Unintended consequences of school closures, found through ongoing systematic literature research in the course of the BETTER project [8], are also to be assessed based on the perspective of the survey participants. Firstly, the participants are asked whether they believe the school closures have had an impact on pupils in general, with the answer options "no effects", "only positive", "only negative" or both "positive and negative effects". The unintended consequences found in the literature are then ranked, including mental health, physical health, children's social behavior, school performance and school connectedness, abuse, suicidality, sleep patterns, healthcare system and parents' financial difficulties. For each of the outcomes listed, sub-items are queried, whereby the importance of the consequences is to be assessed by the survey participants using a five-point Likert scale.

Health literacy is assessed using the validated Health Literacy Survey 2019 short form (HLS19-Q12) [13]. The 12-item questionnaire examines three areas of health literacy, including health care, disease prevention and health promotion. Respondents rate the experienced difficulty of the listed tasks in German language using a four-point Likert scale from "Very easy", "Easy", "Difficult" to "Very difficult". A score is calculated as the percentage of "Very easy" or "Easy" answers in relation to all valid answers.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the characteristics and perceptions of participants. Results will be depicted in tabular form as well as in bar and box plots. Between-group differences will be calculated using parametric t-tests or ANOVA, or their non-parametric equivalents, respectively. We will use R [14] and SPSS [15] for all calculations.

Reporting of the data

Study results will be published in a peer-reviewed article.

Ethical considerations & data security

In this study, we aim to collect data anonymously via SoSci Survey (www.soscisurvey.de), based in Germany. To ensure the anonymity and protection of participants, the following measures are in place:

- SoSci Survey does not allow access to IP address data.
- Age is collected in predefined age groups (e.g., 14-17, 18-24, etc.).
- Gender is queried as male, female or diverse only.
- Only federal states are collected as the place of residence and school location.

No other personal data that could re-identify participants is collected.

The data will be uploaded directly from SoSci Survey's secure servers to the secure servers of the Meduni Vienna (ITSC-secured servers). Only employees of the Meduni Vienna's Institute for Outcomes Research have access to the raw data, and they are bound by confidentiality agreements.

Since the data collection is anonymous, traditional informed consent will not be obtained from participants. Instead, participants will be informed about the study and can access all relevant information via SoSci Survey. By clicking "Ich möchte teilnehmen" (I would like to participate) participants indicate their consent to participate. They can interrupt the survey at any time without providing a reason and can delete any data already entered. Once the questionnaire is completed and submitted, it is not possible to correct or delete the data due to its anonymity. Participants will be informed of this in the introductory text.

All data will be handled in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki and all applicable local regulations. Additionally, all project work will comply with the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The ethics committee of the Medical University of Vienna approved the study (EK Nr: 1763/2024).

REFERENCES

1. Hammerstein, S., König, C., Dreisörner, T., & Frey, A. (2021) Effects of COVID-19-Related School Closures on Student Achievement-A Systematic Review. *Front. Psychol.* 12:746289. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.746289>
2. Lehmann, J., Lechner, V., & Scheithauer, H. (2021). School closures during the COVID-19 pandemic: Psychosocial outcomes in children—A systematic review. *International Journal of Developmental Science*, 15(3-4), 85–111. <https://doi.org/10.3233/DEV-220322>
3. Viner, R., Russell, S., Saullé, R., Croker, H., Stansfield, C., Packer, J., Nicholls, D., Goddings, A. L., Bonell, C., Hudson, L., Hope, S., Ward, J., Schwalbe, N., Morgan, A., & Minozzi, S. (2022). School Closures During Social Lockdown and Mental Health, Health Behaviors, and Well-being Among Children and Adolescents During the First COVID-19 Wave: A Systematic Review. *JAMA pediatrics*, 176(4), 400–409. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamapediatrics.2021.5840>
4. Marques, E. S., Moraes, C. L., Hasselmann, M. H., Deslandes, S. F., & Reichenheim, M. E. (2020). Violence against women, children, and adolescents during the COVID-19 pandemic: overview, contributing factors, and mitigating measures. *Cadernos de saude publica*, 36(4), e00074420. <https://doi.org/10.1590/0102311X00074420>
5. Saullé, R., De Sario, M., Bena, A., Capra, P., Culasso, M., Davoli, M., De Lorenzo, A., Lattke, L. S., Marra, M., Mitrova, Z., Paduano, S., Rabaglietti, E., Sartini, M., & Minozzi, S. (2022). School closures and mental health, wellbeing and health behaviours among children and adolescents during the second COVID-19 wave: a systematic review of the literature. *Epidemiologia e prevenzione*, 46(5-6), 333–352. <https://doi.org/10.19191/EP22.5-6.A542.089>
6. Petretto, D. R., Masala, I., & Masala, C. (2020). School Closure and Children in the Outbreak of COVID-19. *Clinical practice and epidemiology in mental health : CP & EMH*, 16, 189–191. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1745017902016010189>
7. Vorstandlechner, M., Kien, C., Harlfinger, J., Ritschl, V., Bicher, M., Chapman, A., Mosor, E., Schneckenreither, G., Sperl, L., Urach, C., Zauner, G., Gartlehner, G., Popper, N., & Stamm, T. (2023). Stakeholders' perceptions on the impact of political decisions during the COVID-19 pandemic on the health system, and psychosocial, epidemiological and economic outcomes in Vienna and Lower Austria - protocol of a vignette-based qualitative study. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8132238>
8. Ledinger, D., Dobrescu, A., Harlfinger, J., Vorstandlechner, M., Chapman, A., Gadinger, A., Klerings, I., Schmolik, V., Ritschl, V., Stamm, T., & Gartlehner, G. (2023). Unintended consequences of COVID-19-related school closures on children and adolescents: a scoping review protocol. Retrieved August 2, 2024, from <https://osf.io/wbkvn>
9. Holtgrewe, U., Lindorfer, M., Siller, C., & Vana, I. (2021). "Zuhause bekommen wir nur intensive Aufgaben." Lernen im Ausnahmezustand - die Sicht der Schüler_innen. *Zenodo*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4550533>
10. Holtgrewe, U., Vana, I., Lindorfer, M., & Siller, C. (2023). Eine bessere Schule in post-pandemischen Zeiten? Differenzierte Gestaltungswünsche bei Wiener Schüler_innen. *Österreichische Zeitschrift für Soziologie*. 48. 97-114. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11614-023-00513-7>
11. Altrichter, H. & Helm C. (2022). Austrian schools in the COVID-19 pandemic era. *Tertium Comparationis*, 28(3), 300-331. <https://doi.org/10.31244/tc.2022.03.04>
12. Leiner, D. J. (2024). SoSci Survey (Version 3.5.07) [Computer software]. Available at <https://www.soscisurvey.de>
13. Pelikan, J. M., Link, T., Straßmayr, C., Waldherr, K., Alferts, T., Bøggild, H., Griebler, R., Lopatina, M., Mikšová, D., Nielsen, M. G., Peer, S., Vrdelja, M., & HLS19 Consortium of the WHO Action Network M-POHL (2022). Measuring Comprehensive, General Health Literacy in the General Adult Population: The Development and Validation of the HLS19-Q12 Instrument in Seventeen Countries. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 19(21), 14129. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192114129>
14. R Core Team. R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing; R Foundation for Statistical Computing: Vienna, Austria, 2021.
15. IBM Corp. IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 28.0.; IBM Corp.: Armonk, NY, USA, 2021.